

SPEECH CULTURE OF THE TEACHER AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12599619>

Abstract. *Speaking culture education is directly and indirectly related to all subjects at school without exception. A teacher must have a high level of speech culture. Sound is also important. It is necessary for the teacher's speech to be resonant, clear, free of words characteristic of different dialects, and to have high communicative skills. Speech culture is an important tool in acquiring every profession in the world.*

Keywords: *pedagogical culture, communicative speech, diaphragm, diapason, education-education, spirituality-enlightenment, pantomime, national values, aesthetic effect.*

INTRODUCTION.

The place of the mother tongue is extremely important in the spiritual maturity of a person, in the cultural and educational development of society. Language is the most objective and unfading mirror of national spirituality, enlightenment and culture. It is said in the Hadith Sharifs, "The beauty of a person's jewelry is in his language." Our grandfather, the king and poet Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, paid special attention to the simplicity, fluency and clarity of his speech, as well as the high level of speech culture.

Speech culture is an important sign of the cultural and educational development of the society and the spiritual maturity of the nation. Cultural speech in the real sense is one of the extremely important elements of the general cultural level of a person. That is why spiritual and educational reforms are recognized as the priority direction of state policy in our country. Today, the issues of speech culture are more urgent than ever, to improve the teacher's speech culture skills, the cultural speech skills and qualifications of our children, to adequately consider the problems of cultural speech at all stages of the educational process.

There are different professions and different trades in the world. Each of them uses its own working tools. For example: the main working tool of farmers is a hoe. A carpenter's saw, a surgeon's needle, a tailor's needle. With a hoe, a farmer builds a unique garden on barren land, creates beauty, or, if he lacks experience, destroys the life of the land. If the hoe is not sharp, if the farmer himself has not received the hadith of hitting the hoe, woe will come to both the golden soil and the poor farmer. There are professions whose main tool of activity is language, and teaching is at the head of them. No matter what subject he is a specialist in, if the teacher has not acquired the ability to use the language skillfully, that is, if he has not acquired the skills of true cultural speech, if his speech in the class is weak and colorless, how deep and complete is his knowledge. A 45-minute opportunity is painful for him and for the students.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The skill and ability to make a thorough, concise and eloquent speech in one's mother tongue is a necessary quality for both a teacher of mathematics and a teacher of one's mother tongue.

Speaking of speech culture, the culture of speech means that there are a number of communicative qualities such as correctness, accuracy, logicity, expressiveness, richness, purity,

smoothness, which affect the power of the sphere of influence. A speech that embodies all these qualities is considered cultural.

The main issue in speech culture is the appropriate use of language. Therefore, the analysis of real social processes of language use is one of the important areas of this field.

The teacher's speech should be an example for the student in following the standards of literary pronunciation. Violation of the norms of literary pronunciation occurs primarily as a result of dialect. Therefore, it is not easy for the teacher to completely free his and his students' speech from the dialectal articulatory base and phonetic laws of the dialect. As a result of this, there are many mistakes, such as, for example, Bukhara pronunciation of the o sound only in the front-tongue style, Khorezm pronunciation of the o sound mainly in the a style or close to it, Tashkent pronunciation of oshni - oshshi, yuzni-yuzi, karni-korri. Sometimes in the speech of people who know another language perfectly, the defect of saying a certain word according to the pronunciation principle of another language is noticeable. January-January, Japan-Japan, dean-dean, faculty-faculty. Literally reading the written speech also leads to violations of literary pronunciation norms. For example; Did you notice that when you read the word form, it is pronounced with 8 sounds instead of 9, that is, n g is not two sounds, but one sound? Comrade, did you give it to me? such mistakes can be made by the teacher himself.

Speech is verbal communication, that is, the process of communicating with the help of language. In social experience, words that mean something are considered a means of oral communication. Words can be spoken or not, written down, or exchanged with gestures that have some meaning to deaf and dumb people. The relationship between people cannot be compared to telegraphic communication. Emotions of communicators are legitimately involved in human relations. The calculation of the content of communication applies in a certain way to the gaze, attitude, and to those who enter, in this feeling and exciting relationship, which emerges when speech thoughts are combined with considerations, the special non-speech aspect of information exchange is a special non-speech communication content. A teacher should be able to pronounce one word in different tones, giving the student the meaning of sometimes command, sometimes request, sometimes advice, etc. Non-speech communication, gestures, pantomime, variety in the tone of speech will also develop. In the process of communication, feedback is formed, that is, the child can also read the expression on the faces of the conversation, notice the signs of approval or disapproval in his tone, the meaning of the hands and facial movements that complement and reinforce the words of an adult. learns to understand There are several requirements for the communication between the teacher and the student, which must be strictly followed during the pedagogical process.

These requirements are as follows: The teacher's speech should be fluent, the teacher's statement of thoughts should be clear and understandable, and the use of hand, eye, and facial gestures in the speech process should achieve their coherence (connection). , to have a pedagogical effect on the mind, heart, and behavior of students through speech, to take into account their specific characteristics (pedo-psychophysiological) in the process of communicating with the student through the pronunciation of speech, in the pronunciation of the teacher's speech the formation of moral norms, the teacher's ability to communicate with students in a way that is specific to his personality, the teacher's ability not to make methodological and stylistic mistakes in his pronunciation, the teacher's speech skills are developed , the teacher should engage in communication with students using voice monotone positively during the course of the lesson,

educate them in the process of communicating with students, form human qualities in their minds and behavior, determine moral norms, and use the art of artistic words in the process of communication strict adherence, the teacher masters the art of public speaking and then engages in communication, regularly engages in exercises that develop speech pronunciation, the teacher makes reasonable use of pauses and intonations in his speech pronunciation, in the process of communication depends on the teacher learning to think fully and correctly.

The success of communicative speech requires the teacher to develop a number of special abilities: social-perceptive ability, social imagination ability, self-control ability, ability to control one's own mental state in communication, voluntary influence, ability to persuade. The development of general mental and physical characteristics of a person, which creates conditions for successful acquisition of speech skills and abilities, is intended to develop imagination, figurative memory and fantasy.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Voice. Some people have an innate voice, but this too can be broken if not practiced. A person can make his voice strong, flexible, processive. What is the uniqueness of the teacher's voice? First of all, it depends on the strength of the sound and the activity of the organs of its powerful speech apparatus. The flight of sound is the ability to adjust the sound to the distance, to control the sound. Hypkost (flexibility) and podvijnost (mobility) is the ability to easily absorb the sound and adapt it to the listeners. The range is the size of the sound. Its limit is determined by a very high and low tone. Timbre is the color of sound, brightness, and at the same time its softness, warmth, originality. In order to prevent occupational diseases in the teacher, it is necessary to follow sound hygiene. The teacher speaks for 50% of the working time. The teacher should avoid talking for a long time for 2-3 hours after the end of working hours. If necessary, he should speak briefly and slowly. It is necessary to pay attention to this when setting the lesson schedule. After 3-4 hours of lessons, the speech apparatus gets tired, after which the voice should rest for 1 hour. A teacher with many years of experience gets tired in 2-3 hours and needs to rest for 2 hours. It is necessary to pay attention to the upper respiratory tract, nervous system, and diet. Diction is the correctness and precision in the pronunciation of words, syllables, and sounds. Improving diction is related to processing the movement of speech organs. Special exercises are administered. Rhythmicity is the complete continuity in the pronunciation of certain syllables, and at the same time the stage of speech organization. This is an important element of speech, and sometimes intonation and pauses have a stronger emotional impact than the words themselves. The speed of speech depends on the individual quality of the teacher, the content of his speech and the state of communication. Different nationalities have different tempo of speech. About 120 words per minute in Russians, up to 120-150 words in English. According to research, it is correct for a teacher to speak 60 words per minute in grades 5-6, and 75 words per minute in grades 9-11. The teacher should speak the difficult part of the topic at a slow pace, and then faster. As a rule, the speech slows down in conclusion. Speech technique. Most of the study time (1/4, 1/2) is related to the teacher's speech. Therefore, the students' understanding of the educational material is related to the perfection of the teacher's speech. Some believe that sound and its timbre are innate. But the current experimental physiology reveals that it is possible to completely reconstruct the sound. Today, based on the experience of theater pedagogy, it is planned to work on such complexes as speech breathing, sound, diction, rhythmicity. breath In addition to providing life to the body, breath also acts as the energy base of speech. Speech breath is called phonological breath (phono-

sound). In everyday life, our speech is dialogic, and breathing is not difficult. Unchanged breathing and unaccustomed breathing cause difficulties when the teacher talks a lot and gives a lecture: there may be cases of reddening of the face and fatigue. Depending on which muscles are involved in breathing, there are 4 types of breathing: the muscles that lift the upper part of the chest are involved. This is a weak, upper breath, and only the upper part of the lungs is active; breathing through the chest is carried out by the muscles between the ribs. Diaphragm is less active, exhalation is weak; diaphragmatic breathing - due to the change in the volume of the chest, contraction of the diaphragm; breathing through the diaphragm and ribs - a comprehensive change in the volume of the diaphragm, respiratory muscles between the ribs and in the abdomen are also involved. This breath is correct and it is the basis for speech breath.

For young teachers, it is necessary to briefly dwell on the breathing technique: Upper breath is carried out by the rise and fall of the muscles of the shoulders and chest.

This causes weak, shallow breathing, in which only the upper part of the lungs is actively working. Breathing with the chest is carried out through the intercostal spaces and muscles. In this case, there will be a change in the cross section of the chest. Due to the lack of movement of the diaphragm, breathing is shallow. Breathing through the diaphragm - as a result of the longitudinal change in the volume of the chest, the diaphragm is reduced, on the basis of which the intercostal muscles are shortened.

Breathing through the diaphragmatic rib - transverse and longitudinal contraction of the diaphragm occurs between the ribs. This is the most correct breathing and is the basis of speech breathing because it is calculated. Among the teachers, there are many people who are naturally pleasant and have beautiful voices. But no matter how nice the voice is, it will deteriorate, wear out, and grow old without special exercises over the years. Each person's voice is unique, strong and harsh, etc. Four causes of voice disorders have been identified: Due to daily voice strain; Due to the weakness of the voice apparatus; Non-compliance with hygiene rules; Congenital weakness of the vocal apparatus. It was found that 50% of teachers have voice disorders due to the strain of the voice apparatus. This is the result of speaking out loud. The human voice apparatus consists of three parts: generator, energy and resonator parts. Sound generation occurs in the vocal folds and barriers in the oral cavity, as a result of which noisy sounds occur. In the resonator system - larynx, nasopharynx, oral cavity, speech rhythm and dynamic development are ensured. energetic system - related to external breathing, forms air waves and volume, and causes the origin of sound. In order to increase the effectiveness of teaching and to have a positive educational effect, the teacher should also have the skills of acting and directing. In particular, it is necessary for teachers of literature, art, and history to have acting skills. Acting skills are needed when characterizing certain themes, images, historical characters, and directorial skills are needed when training these characteristics in students. In addition to what has been said, they help the teacher to influence not only the intellect of the students, but also their feelings when dealing with young people, to give them the full experience of having an emotional-valuable attitude towards the scientist. . Thus, if the teacher cultivates the above-mentioned pedagogical technique skills, he will succeed in the field of teaching and educating young people and developing them as individuals. The above-mentioned professional qualifications are obtained on the basis of the teacher's knowledge of academic and special subjects, the desire to acquire pedagogical skills, interest in his profession, and a sense of duty and responsibility. And they help young people in education, upbringing, organization, promotion, independent education. Scholars of school science say that the expected

goal will be achieved if the above mentioned and classified pedagogic technique skills are used as a whole, not individually. For example, the implementation of speech techniques combined with emotions, mime, pantomime skills is based on the ability to think clearly and analyze calmly in an unexpected pedagogical situation with words, tone of speech, look, gesture. , will be appropriate. These characteristics are formed on the basis of the individual psychological and physiological qualities of the pedagogue. Individual pedagogical technique depends on the teacher's age, gender, client, character, health and anatomical-physiological characteristics. Thus, if the teacher-educator cultivates the above skills, if he thoroughly learns their content, he will have the opportunity to master the speech technique, and he will lead the teacher to pedagogical skills. The concept of speech is closely related to the concept of communicative behavior of the teacher.

The communicative behavior of the teacher is not only the process of speaking and giving information, but also the creation of an emotional psychological environment for the interaction of the pedagogue and the student, the organization of the speech that affects the relationship and work style between them and the development of it. the teacher's speaking skills are also taken into account. The teacher's speech should meet certain requirements, that is, it should correspond to the necessary communicative qualities. Speech should conform to several norms: modern norms, expressive, literary language norms. Communicative qualities of the teacher's speech, such as correctness, accuracy, appropriateness, lexical richness, expressiveness and purity, determine the culture of the teacher's speech. Pedagogical speech in accordance with the purpose is characterized by its logic, reliability, observation. One of the functions of speech is to ensure the complete transfer of knowledge. There is a direct connection between the communicative specificity of the teacher's speech and the acceptance and retention of knowledge by students. Speech can enable or hinder this. The speech of the teacher should not only give information, but should affect the mind and intuition of the student, encourage them to think. The teacher's speech, secondly, the speech of the student's effective educational activity, should first of all provide an effective educational listener in the lesson. While listening to the teacher's speech, the student performs a number of operations: he clarifies the given information in a visual form, reacts to it with his own knowledge, remembers, follows the logic of the speech, the development of thoughts. High-pitched, high-pitched voices tire children. Effectiveness of the educational-knowledge process is also affected by the style of communicative behavior chosen by the teacher in the lesson. The teacher often interrupts the student's answer by using words that express dissatisfaction, such as "shut up", "sit", "stop", "shut up". The teacher says things like "you don't know anything as usual", "you understood it from somewhere", which leads to a violation of the student's attitude, a decrease in mental activity, and the emergence of non-pedagogical situations. It is to ensure a productive interaction between the speech and the teacher. Speech also plays the role of managing the student-teacher relationship. Everything is important here: how the teacher addresses the students, how he greets them, how he sets his requirements, how he warns, how he expresses his wishes; impotence of speech, facial expression, look also affects the child. Their importance becomes even greater in extracurricular communication. A lot depends on the teacher's individual style of communication (fear-based, game-based, friendly communication), and social characteristics within the framework of communication. Another feature of oral speech is its improvisational character. An experienced teacher speaks without looking at the text or synopsis, the student listens to him and sees that the words and expressions are caught at once. There is such

a situation that it is as if the teacher is revealing this truth and thoughts with the students for the first time.

CONCLUSION

Summing up, it can be said that it is one of the most important integral signs of the general speech culture of a teacher at the required level. Live sound speech and the correct eventing of all its elements means the total speech technique of skills and competences. A teacher who is devoted to his profession appears in the eyes of his students as a flawless and knowledgeable, valuable teacher. It is up to each teacher to keep it. It is desirable for a teacher to always work on himself, to be aware of the news, to look positively at innovations, to be an innovator himself. In small classes, uztov speech is fluent, sonorous, free of various malicious means, and has a positive effect on the general educational process. The teacher's voice, pronunciation, diction, and the lively speech in general always serve as a unique reference model for students.

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